

MEDICAL SCIENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969377>

METHODS OF TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF CHRONIC APICAL PERIODONTITIS

Abstract.

*In modern dentistry, there are many methods for treating and diagnosing chronic apical periodontitis, but the prevalence of caries complications is 35-47%. According to O.P. Maksimova, in 2005, almost every patient had 4 to 8 teeth with caries complications. Odontogenic infections play a significant role in damaging internal organs such as the heart, liver, and kidneys. In most cases, apical periodontitis is caused by microflora consisting of various opportunistic microorganisms. In 2017, E.N. Kogina and L.P. Gerasimova discovered a high frequency of bacterial and fungal flora in the root canals of teeth, with the presence of aggressive *Prevotella intermedia* and *Fusobacterium* bacteria. The effectiveness of endodontic therapy depends on the treatment of the root canals, but even after treatment, microorganisms can persist, which can affect the effectiveness of therapy. The purpose of the study: to conduct a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of treating destructive forms of periodontitis. Ninety-two patients with chronic apical periodontitis without a history of endodontic intervention were observed. Clinical examination, treatment and X-ray control were carried out after 6 and 12 months.*

Keywords: *destructive periodontitis, optical density of bone tissue, cytokine profile, microbiological examination, endodontic treatment*

Today, in modern dentistry, there are numerous methods of treatment and diagnosis of chronic apical periodontitis, but despite this, the prevalence of caries complications is from 35 to 47% of cases [1, 2, 10]. According to O.P. Maksimova, during the dispensary observation of patients in 2005, almost every patient was found to have from 4 to 8 teeth with caries complications that required repeated treatment [8]. In addition, data from domestic and foreign authors indicate a significant role of odontogenic infection in the damage of internal organs: heart, liver, kidneys, joints and other organs [9, 11, 12]. Therefore, issues related to diagnosis, treatment and assessment of remote results remain relevant to this day. The cause of the development of apical periodontitis in the vast majority of cases is the microflora, which is part of the root canal system and periapical tissues. Microbial symbiosis is represented by associations of various types of opportunistic microorganisms: various types of bacteria of the genus *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus*, bacteria of the class *Spirochaetes*, etc. A certain place in the pathogenesis of periodontitis is also occupied by anaerobic microflora, for the growth of which favorable conditions arise in the root canals. In addition to these microorganisms, various types of fungi of the genus *Candida* and protozoa are found in the root canals [9, 11, 12]. According to E.N. Kogina and L.P. Gerasimova, a microbiological study of the contents of the root canals in destructive forms of periodontitis conducted in 2017 showed a high frequency of bacterial and fungal flora, its quantity ranged from 4 to 5.8 lg CFU/ml. The most aggressive

facultative anaerobic gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria *Prevotella intermedia*, *Fusobacterium*, *Actinomyces* spp., which belong to the periodontopathogenic group and have pronounced toxicity, were identified [3, 4]. A necessary condition determining the effectiveness of endodontic therapy is medicinal treatment of the root canals of teeth, which provides an active effect on the flora of macro- and micro-canals by means of specially developed antiseptics [9, 10]. It has been established that even after instrumental and medicinal treatment, microorganisms can be found in the root canals. This means that even if general bacterial eradication is not achieved, at least a reduction in the species representation of microorganisms is achieved. In total, there can be up to 5 species in concentrations from 2 to 5 lg CFU/ml in the sample. Most often these are gram-positive bacteria *Streptococcus*, *Actinomyces*, *Propionibacterium*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, etc. Thus, the presence of surviving microorganisms in the root canals can affect the effectiveness of the treatment [9-11]. Based on the literature data [1, 2, 9, 10], periodontitis is the most common reason for people to seek dental care and is characterized by a variety of microbial flora in the root canal, which significantly complicates the correct choice of treatment, directing us to search for new effective treatments and diagnostic methods for chronic periodontitis. The purpose of the study: to conduct a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of treating destructive forms of periodontitis. MATERIALS AND METHODS We observed 92 patients aged 25 to 35

years with destructive forms of chronic apical periodontitis without a history of endodontic intervention and a state of periodontal tissues in the remission stage. The exclusion criteria for patients were general somatic pathologies, pregnancy, obliterated and curved root canals. All patients underwent a clinical examination, endodontic treatment with preventive examinations and X-ray control 6 and 12 months after the treatment. A total of 92 teeth were treated, 42 (46%) single-rooted and 50 (54%) multi-rooted. Additionally, a radiovisiographic study (RVG) of the periapical tissues in the destruction focus was performed with determination of the optical density of bone tissue — densitometry, as well as an immunological study — with determination of the cytokine profile of oral fluid and a microbiological study of the root canal contents before treatment and before permanent filling. RVG was performed on the Trophy 2000 device (France). When measuring the optical density of the periapical tissues in the image, the shape of the focus was visually assessed, then a straight line was drawn in the program along the destruction focus so that it passed through the center of the lesion. Based on the resulting densitogram, the state of the destruction focus in the periapical region was assessed, as well as the restoration of bone tissue in the destruction focus during treatment. The values of bone tissue density in the periapical region within the range of 130.5 ± 4.4 units were taken as normal [5]. An immunological study to determine the cytokine profile of oral fluid (interleukins IL-1 α , IL-1 β , IL-8, tumor necrosis factor-alpha — TNF- α) was performed before treatment and before permanent root canal filling. The concentrations of IL-1 α — 3.8 ± 0.8 , IL-1 β — 3.5 ± 0.7 , IL-8 — 2.7 ± 0.6 and TNF- α — 3.2 ± 0.4 pg/ml were taken as normal [6]. The concentration of cytokines was determined by solid-phase enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) with Vector-Best reagents (Novosibirsk) on a Labline-90 analyzer (Austria). Microbiological examination of the root canal contents was performed before and after treatment with transportation of the biomaterial to the laboratory for 1-2 hours at a temperature of 2-4°C, followed by primary seeding on special nutrient media for aerobes and anaerobes, cultivation and identification. The quantitative and qualitative composition was determined by a standard method. Identification of microorganisms was performed by morphological, tinctorial and cultural features. The species affiliation was established based on biochemical properties using the ATB Expression analyzer (bioMérieux, France) using specific test systems from the same manufacturer. To access the root canal orifices, all patients had their carious cavity prepared and opened after adequate anesthesia and isolation of the working field with a cofferdam, and the products of necrotic decay of the pulp tissue were removed. Mechanical treatment of the root canals was performed using a Reciproc machine instrument (VDW, Germany) using a multifunctional endodontic stepper motor with controlled force Silver Reciproc (VDW). This was followed by treatment with a 3% sodium hypochlorite solution and 17% ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid solution with ultrasonic activation until a visually clear irrigant solution

was determined. Depending on the subsequent treatment, the patients were divided into two groups. Group I (52 teeth) was treated according to our own patented scheme [7]. After electrophoresis with 1% dimethyl sulfoxide solution (2 procedures from the anode and 2 from the cathode), a mixture of preparations containing sodium aminodihydrophthalazinedione, paste with hydroxyapatite, tricalcium phosphate, barium sulfate and a combination of organic anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial preparations, prepared ex tempore, was introduced into the root canal. Then, the mucous membrane of the gum in the area of the root apex projection was exposed to IR radiation with a wavelength of 850 nm four times for 5 minutes using the ALST-01 Optodan device (Russia) using a magnetic tip. After that, all root canals and the tooth cavity were filled using any of the generally accepted methods. In Group II (40 teeth), the treatment was performed in a standard way: the root canal was temporarily filled with a paste based on calcium hydroxide for 14 days, after which all root canals and the tooth cavity were filled using any of the generally accepted methods. RESULTS: During the clinical examination, 5 patients complained of periodic pain when chewing, 35 were referred by an orthopedic dentist to prepare teeth for a supporting structure, the rest came for a preventive examination. All patients had a discolored crown of the causal tooth, the carious cavity communicated with the tooth cavity, probing of the crown and root canals of the causal tooth was painless, the EOD value was over 100 μ A, indicating necrosis of the coronal and root pulp of the tooth. No changes in the skin were detected during the visual examination, and regional lymph nodes were not palpated. According to the X-ray venography, the optical density of bone tissue before treatment was more than two times lower in all patients. Six months after the treatment, it reached the norm in patients of group I, and was one third below the norm in group II. After 12 months, the bone density in Group I remained within the normal range, while in Group II it was still 20% lower, which demonstrates the advantage of our treatment method. The summarized results of the immunological study of cytokine concentrations before and after treatment are presented in Table 2. In both groups, before treatment, all the studied parameters were reliably approximately 3-5 times higher than normal. After treatment, cytokine concentrations in Group I significantly decreased and did not exceed the norm by more than 1.2-1.9 times, while in Group II they exceeded it by 2.4-3.7 times. Microbiological examination of the root canal contents before treatment revealed a significant diversity of microbial flora, which did not differ fundamentally in Groups I and II. In the samples, among anaerobic and facultative-anaerobic streptococci, the dominant position was occupied by *S. intermedius* (60-65%), *S. sanguis* (53.8%), *S. milleri* (50%), *S. viridans* (42.3%), *S. mitis* (44.2%) and *Peptostreptococcus* spp. (21-25%). Facultative-anaerobic enterococci were detected in 30-45% of samples, and among staphylococci, *S. aureus* (22-25%), *S. epidermidis* (17-25%), *S. hyicus* (10-15%) and *S. intermedius* (4-15%) were isolated. Aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria such as *Corynebacterium*

spp. were found in 19–25% of samples, and Actinomyces spp. in 50–55%. Also detected were gram-negative anaerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria Fusobacterium (6–15%), Escherichia coli (30–65%), Prevotella intermedia (6–10%), and Candida albicans fungi (10–20%). Quantitative analysis revealed high concentrations of facultative anaerobic bacteria (Streptococcus, Enterococcus spp., and Escherichia coli) within 5.2 lg CFU/ml. The contamination of Peptostreptococcus spp. was lower — 4.4 lg CFU/ml. Aerobic (Corynebacterium spp.) and facultative anaerobic staphylococci (S. aureus, S. epidermidis, S. hyicus and S. intermedium) were detected on average at 4.4 lg CFU/ml. Periodontopathogenic bacteria Actinomyces spp., bacteroids Prevotella intermedia and Fusobacterium (4.9 lg CFU/ml), and fungi of the genus Candida albicans (4.3 lg CFU/ml) were present in comparable quantities. After repeated examination (before permanent filling) of microbial flora in patients of group I, the frequency of detection of bacteria decreased sharply, only some species were found in isolated cases: Streptococcus intermedius, Streptococcus sanguis and Enterococcus spp. in extremely small quantities, no more than 3.0 lg CFU/ml. Endodontic treatment according to the scheme developed by us led to a decrease in the number of bacteria to single viable cells, which allows to provide conditions for maintaining a chronic inflammatory process. Repeated examination in group II was also carried out after 2 weeks, before permanent filling of root canals. The most resistant to endodontic treatment were streptococci and actinomycetes bacteria, which were found in 18 patients, Fusobacterium and Candida albicans were isolated in 10% of cases, and Enterococcus spp. - in 15% of cases. The frequency of isolation of microbial species decreased along with the decrease in the number of viable bacteria, which was reliably lower than before the treatment and did not exceed 3.1 lg CFU/ml. CONCLUSIONS

1. Determination of optical density is an objective method of dynamic monitoring of the condition of periapical tissues in the center of destruction in chronic periodontitis before, during and after treatment. According to the analysis, statistically significant differences are observed between the results of the method of endodontic treatment of destructive forms of periodontitis developed by us and the standard method. Optical density indicators in group I after 12 months were within the normal range, and the indicators of group II were statistically significantly lower, which indicates favorable dynamics of treatment according to our scheme.

2. When studying the cytokine profile of oral fluid, statistically significant differences with the norm were obtained in the direction of a significant increase. The concentration of cytokines in group II was 1.3-2 times higher than in group I. Thus, the level of cytokines after endodontic treatment by our method was closer to the norm, which indicates the effectiveness of therapeutic treatment.

3. Microbiological and microscopic studies of the root canal contents showed a high frequency of bacterial and fungal flora with its concentration within 4.0-5.8 lg CFU/ml. At the same time, the most aggressive

facultative anaerobic bacteria Prevotella intermedia, Fusobacterium, Actinomyces spp. were identified, which belong to the periodontopathogenic group and have pronounced toxicity.

4. Complex endodontic treatment of destructive forms of periodontitis both according to our and the traditional scheme led to a decrease in the number of bacteria in the root canal, but the scheme we proposed was more effective. Representatives of some pathogenic bacteria (Streptococcus intermedius, Streptococcus sanguis, Enterococcus spp.) were found in root canals only in isolated cases and in extremely small quantities (up to 3.0 lg CFU/ml).

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